

Simple and Complex Metallic Salts of Thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic Acid.

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The potassium salt of thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic acid has been described by Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 5, 325). The free acid was subsequently isolated and its alkali and alkaline earth salts were also studied (Rây and Maulik, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 355). The present work was undertaken to study the preparation and properties of a number of other metallic and metal-ammonium salts.

The following list shows the compositions of the compounds prepared.

- I. $\text{BeO} \cdot \text{Be}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- II. $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- III. $\text{Mn}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- IV. $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$
- V. $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2]_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and in the anhydrous state.
- VI. $[\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_3)_4]_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$
- VII. $[\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_3)_2]_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- VIII. $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_5]_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$
- IX. $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_2]_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- X. $\text{Ag}_4[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$
- XI. $\text{Ag}_4[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 4\frac{1}{2} \text{NH}_3, 6\frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Basic beryllium salt (I).—A freshly prepared solution of the free complex acid (Rây and Maulik, *loc. cit.*) was saturated with beryllium oxide; the solution was filtered and kept in vacuum over sulphuric acid. When the liquid was reduced to half its volume, it was filtered again and evaporated finally to dryness in a vacuum. The orange-red substance is very soluble in water. This property is characteristic of many beryllium salts. (Found: Be, 6.95; Co, 15.54; $\text{BeO} \cdot \text{Be}_2[(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Be, 7.1; Co, 15.5 per cent).

Manganese potassium salt (II).—Manganese chloride (2.5 g.) dissolved in the least quantity of water was added, drop by drop, with constant stirring to a cold saturated solution of 5 g. of the potassium salt (Rây, *loc. cit.*). The precipitate, formed, was filtered and washed with ice-cold water, then with cold dilute alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. When dried in air, the substance formed a pale yellow crystalline powder. (Found: Co, 11.56; K, 15.45; Mn, 10.83. $\text{MnK}_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.66; K, 15.41; Mn, 10.90 per cent).

Manganese salt (III).—Calcium salt (2.5 g.) (Rây and Maulik, *loc. cit.*) was added to the solution of an excess of manganese chloride (25 g. in 15 c.c. water). The mixture containing the thick precipitate was carefully heated in the water-bath till it completely went into solution. This was then filtered and allowed to evaporate at the ordinary temperature in air. The crystals formed, were drained, washed at first with cold water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. (Found: Co, 11.47; Mn, 21.30. $\text{Mn}_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3] 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.37; Mn, 21.16 per cent).

Tetra- and di-ammonium copper salt (IV & V).—Calcium salt (5 g.) dissolved in the least quantity of cold water, was added to cold saturated solution of crystallised cupric chloride (5 g.) with constant stirring. The gelatinous precipitate, produced, was filtered through a Buchner funnel, and the mother liquor was drained as far as possible. The solid mass was then transferred to a small conical flask with about 25 c.c. of water. The flask was cooled in ice and ammonia gas was passed through the mixture. The substance gradually went into solution. On maintaining the current of ammonia gas for about 2 hours, blue crystals separated from the solution. These were purified by dissolving them in the least quantity of water and saturating the solution again with ammonia gas at a low temperature. The blue crystals, reprecipitated, were drained, washed with a cold saturated solution of ammonia, followed by ice-cold alcoholic ammonia. They were then dried over quick lime in an atmosphere of ammonia gas. (Found: Co, 10.52; Cu, 22.35; NH_3 , 24.12. $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]_2 [(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$ requires Co, 10.4; Cu, 22.38; NH_3 , 24.15 per cent).

When the above compound was exposed to the atmospheric air, it lost ammonia and turned green. When the weight became constant it was analysed. (Found: Co, 10.73; Cu, 22.78; NH_3 , 12.27,

$[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2]_2[(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{Co}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3]3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10.75; Cu, 22.95; NH_3 , 12.39 per cent).

When dried over quick lime, the green crystals lost their water of crystallisation. No loss of ammonia, however, occurred. (Found: Cu, 25.57; NH_3 , 13.69. The anhydrous salt requires Cu, 25.47; NH_3 , 13.74 per cent).

Tetra- and di-ammonium zinc salt (VI & VII).—A solution of calcium salt (5 g.) in about 20 c.c. of water was added with constant stirring to a solution of an equal weight of zinc chloride in 25 c.c. of water. The jelly-like mass, thus obtained, was drained as thoroughly as possible and then transferred to a small conical flask with a little water. This was treated with ammonia gas at low temperature till a clear solution was obtained. This was filtered, and the filtrate was cooled in ice and saturated with ammonia gas. The crystals, separated, were purified by dissolving them in water, and saturating the solution once again with ammonia gas. The pure crystals were filtered and washed with cold concentrated ammonia followed by alcoholic ammonia. These were dried over quick lime in an atmosphere of ammonia. (Found: Co, 10.31; NH_3 , 23.92; Zn, 23.14. $[\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_3)_4]_2[(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{Co}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$ requires Co, 10.41; NH_3 , 23.98; Zn, 22.93 per cent).

When the purified crystals were dried to constant weight in air, they lost ammonia and changed to the diammino compound. (Found: Co, 10.34; NH_3 , 11.85; Zn, 22.84. $[\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_3)_2]_2[(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{Co}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3]4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10.34; NH_3 , 11.91; Zn, 22.77 per cent).

Penta- and di-ammonium nickel salts (VIII & IX).—A solution of calcium salt (5 g.) was added to a solution of an equal weight of nickel chloride crystals in the cold. The precipitate obtained was drained and treated with ammonia as described under the copper salt. The crystals separated were dissolved in dilute ammonia and reprecipitated from the solution by the passage of ammonia gas. The yellowish-green crystals, thus obtained, were dried over quick lime in an atmosphere of ammonia. (Found: Co, 9.18; Ni, 18.24; NH_3 , 26.65. $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_5]_2[(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{Co}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3]3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co 9.19; Ni, 18.28; NH_3 , 26.46 per cent). The composition of this compound is rather unusual, as the nickel atom appears to have a co-ordination number of 5 with respect to ammonia. It may, however, be represented as $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2[(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{Co}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3]\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

When exposed to the atmosphere, the yellowish green crystals rapidly lost a part of its ammonia and turned green. (Found: Ni, 19.68; NH₃, 11.52. [Ni (NH₃)₂]₂ [(CN)₅·Co·S₂O₃] 6H₂O requires Ni, 19.75; NH₃, 11.44 per cent).

Silver salt (X).—A cold aqueous solution of the potassium salt (3 g.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring to an ice-cold solution of silver nitrate (5 g.). The precipitated silver salt was washed by decantation with water at 0° till free from soluble matter. It was then filtered at the pump, washed with cold alcohol and dried over sulphuric acid. The substance formed a light yellow powder. (Found: Ag, 59.1; Co, 8.04. Ag₄[(CN)₅·Co·S₂O₃] requires Ag, 58.94; Co, 80.5 per cent).

Silver ammonium salt (XI).—The freshly prepared silver compound was dissolved in concentrated ammonia in the cold, and the solution was saturated with ammonia gas at 0°. The crystals separated were drained, washed at first with cold alcoholic ammonia and then with ether. The compound is extremely unstable, and rapidly turns black due to decomposition. (Found: Ag, 46.33; Co, 6.31; NH₃, 8.41. Ag₄[(CN)₅·Co·S₂O₃].4½NH₃, 6½H₂O requires Ag, 46.67; Co, 6.37; NH₃, 8.31 per cent).

The composition indicates that 8 silver atoms are associated with 9 ammonia molecules, showing that the co-ordination number for silver varies between 2 to 1 here.

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